

Assessment of the Level of Heavy Metals from Industrial Effluent and Simulated Solution: Remediation Using Almond Seed Shell as Adsorbent in Calabar Metropolis

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Abstract

Almond seed shells are effective at reducing toxic metal concentrations due to their high adsorption capacity, natural abundance, and chemical composition, which include cellulose and lignin with binding sites for metal ions. This study focuses on optimizing conditions to enhance the removal efficiency of heavy metals (Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Zn^{2+}) from waste water and aqueous solution. Factors such as pH, temperature, and contact time were explored to understand their impact on the adsorption. At 30 °C, it was observed that the adsorption rate of almond seed shell (AMS) increases with higher initial metal ion concentrations. The adsorption capacity of AMS for various metals from aqueous solutions, considering variables such as concentration, pH, temperature, and adsorption time were investigated. AMS proved to be cost-effective adsorbent for removing low concentrations of heavy metals from aqueous solutions. The adsorption capacity decreased over time as more adsorbate covered the adsorbent surface, with the order of adsorption being Mn^{2+} , $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Pb}^{2+}$, $\text{Fe}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+}$. The effect of temperature, (ranging from 30 to 60 °C) on metal ion removal was also examined. It was observed that higher temperatures enhance the adsorption efficiency. Obtained Activation energy (E_a) values of 44.56 kJ/mol and 64.27 kJ/mol, indicate slower adsorption rates for Fe and Zn. It can be said that almond seed shells are a cost-effective, accessible natural material suitable for adsorbing Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , from aqueous solutions. The Freundlich adsorption model fit the experimental data well, with greater than 1. The adsorption kinetics follow a pseudo-second-order model, suggesting that chemical adsorption is the rate-determining step.

Keywords: Adsorption, Heavy Metals, Environmental Contaminants, Almond Seed Shell, Pollutant.

INTRODUCTION

A recent report has revealed that approximately 2 million people in South-western Nigeria alone could potentially be poisoned by lead (Pb) and mercury (Hg) from illegal mining operations [1]. This highlights the need to investigate levels of toxic trace metals in the country. Contamination of natural water bodies by industrial effluents has become a significant challenge in developing and densely populated countries like Nigeria. Estuaries and inland water bodies, which serve as the main sources of drinking water in Nigeria, are frequently polluted by the activities of nearby populations and industrial facilities [2]. Heavy metals from industrial effluents are a critical environmental challenge in Nigeria. Water that is not properly treated and have heavy metals as contaminants can be harmful to aquatic life, and thereby pose risks to public health. The presence of heavy metals in wastewater poses serious health and environmental risks.

Exposure to these metals can lead to various health issues, including cancer, neurological disorders, and organ damage. Other Environmental consequences include water pollution, soil contamination, and

harmful impact on aquatic ecosystems. Heavy Metals are considered as primary pollutants due to their toxicity and mobility in natural water systems [3]. Discharge from industrial waste contains various organic and inorganic pollutants. Most of these pollutants are heavy metals which can be toxic and or carcinogenic which are harmful to humans and other living species [4,5]. Common heavy metals include: lead (Pb), mercury (Hg), cadmium (Cd). [6]. The harmful effects of heavy metals on human health have been increased by industrial and anthropogenic activities and modern-day industrialization. Contamination of water and air by toxic metals is an environmental concern and hundreds of millions of people are being affected around the world. The toxicity and carcinogenicity of heavy metals are dose dependent.

High-dose exposure leads to sever responses in animal and human which causes more DNA damage and neuropsychiatric disorders [7]. Heavy metals of most concerns from various industries includes lead (Pb), zinc (Zn) copper (Cu), arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), nickel (Ni), mercury (Hg) [8].

These various metals originate from sources such as metal complexes, dyes, pesticides, fertilizers, fixing agents (which are added to dyes to improve dyes absorption onto the fibers), Mordants, pigments and bleaching agents [9].

Numerous techniques for removing heavy metal ions from wastewater have been reported [10]. Mirmohammadmakki *et al.* [11] conducted a pivotal study on environmental pollution caused by toxic metals, particularly their impact on agricultural and horticultural crops. Their research explored the use of almond shells, both untreated and treated with phosphoric acid, as a novel biosorbent for heavy metals in soil. Raji *et al.* [12] gave an in-depth review of the adsorption mechanisms, kinetics, and applications of various adsorbents used in the removal of heavy metals from wastewater. The study offers a comprehensive analysis of the different processes involved in adsorption, including the interaction between adsorbents and metal ions, the factors influencing adsorption kinetics, and the efficiency of various materials in wastewater remediation. Study conducted by Yang *et al.* [13] provides a review of the role of surface functional groups in carbon-based adsorbents and their effectiveness in removing heavy metals from aqueous solutions. Mnasri-Ghnimi and Frini-Srasra [14] reported the application of single and mixed pillared clays for the removal of heavy metals, specifically cadmium (Cd^{2+}), cobalt (Co^{2+}), and copper (Cu^{2+}), from aqueous solutions. Their research focused on understanding the adsorption behavior of these metals under varying conditions, including pH, contact time, initial concentration, and temperature.

Duan *et al.* [15] also offered a review on the removal of heavy metals from aqueous solutions using carbon-based adsorbents. The research focused on the effectiveness of various carbon-based materials, ranging from traditional biochar and activated carbon to more advanced materials such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and graphene (GN). Karim *et al.* [16] reported their research results revealing that dietary fibers exhibit significant adsorption capacities for heavy metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), and arsenic (As). The efficiency of adsorption was found to be influenced by various factors, including the composition of the fibers, surface area, and the presence of functional groups. The research highlighted that the adsorption mechanisms in these fibers typically involve ion exchange, complexation, and physical adsorption, processes that are heavily dependent on the chemical nature of the fibers. Upadhyay *et al.* [17] experimented on the use of chitosan-based adsorbents for the removal of heavy metal ions from aqueous solutions, the study provides an extensive

overview of the advancements in chitosan-based adsorbents for heavy metal removal, underscoring the effectiveness of modified chitosan materials and their potential for large-scale applications in industrial wastewater treatment. Arfi *et al.* [18], also studied Adsorptive removal of cationic and anionic dyes from aqueous solution by utilizing almond shell as bioadsorbent. The study indicated that almond shell was an effective bioadsorbent for removing Malachite Green (spontaneous process) but not Eriochrome Black T (non-spontaneous process) from aqueous solutions [19],[20] [21]

In developed countries legislation is becoming increasingly stringent for heavy metals limits in wastewater. The Maximum Contaminants Level (MCL) of heavy metals that is allowed in drinking water established by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) of Cu, Li, Ni, and Pb are 1.3 ppm, 0ppm, 0.2ppm and 0.006 ppm respectively (USEPA 2009). Table 1 below outlines the permissible limits of heavy metals in water, along side standards set by World Health Organization (WHO) and the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA). Key metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), mercury (Hg), have strict limits, reflecting their toxicity. Notably, zinc (Zn) and copper (Cu) have higher allowable concentrations, given their essential roles in biological systems, though still regulated to avoid any harm.

Table. 1 Permissible limit (ppm) of heavy metals in water

Heavy metal ions	Permissible limits (ppm)	WHO	US EPA
As(III)/As(v)	0.05	0.05	0.01
Pb(II)	0.05	0.05	0.015
Cd(II)	0.005	0.005	0.005
Cr(VI)/Cr(III)	0.05	0.05	0.05
Hg(II)	0.001	0.001	0.002
Zn(II)	5.0	5.0	5.0
Cu(II)	1.5	1.5	1.3
Co(II)	0.01	0.01	

This study was on the analysis of common heavy metals that are prevalent in the industrial areas of Calabar Metropolis. The specific metals of interest include iron (Fe), lead (Pb), manganese (Mn), copper (Cu), and zinc (Zn). The study aimed to assess the concentration levels of these heavy metals in the environment, understand their potential sources, and evaluate the associated risks to human health and the ecosystem. The research used simulation studies to evaluate and compare how well almond seed (*Prunus amygdalus*) shell can be used as a natural adsorbent for the removal of heavy metals (like lead, iron, zinc,

manganese and copper) from contaminated water or environments. There is currently dearth literature on the process of determination and remediation of the level of heavy metals from industrial effluents in Calabar Metropolis using almond seed shells as an adsorbent. Therefore, this research work focused on these heavy metals and their removal from waste water, industrial effluents and simulated aqueous solution. by almond seed shells in Calabar metropolis

METHODS

Pulverization of Almond Seed Shells (*Prunus amygdalus*)

The respective almonds seed shells were emptied into clean stainless plates placed in a regulated oven and dried at 35 °C for 8 hours. The samples were disintegrated with the aid of the jaw crusher into a well clean mortar and placed in the pulverizing machine. The machine was switched on and allowed to operate for 30 minutes. The pulverized samples were emptied into a 150 mm sieve and shaken. The powdered samples retained at the base of the sieve. These were emptied into a sample bags and labelled in accordance with the sample location number.

Sampling of Industrial Effluents and Determination of Heavy Metals from Effluents Samples

Industrial waste water from three locations, Niger Mill evacuation point, Essien Town and WAPI Junction all in Calabar Municipality LGA, Cross River State were collected and the samples were preserved by ice packs and pH taken *in situ*. Digestion of effluent samples for metal ion determination before adsorption studies were done according to AOAC [23]. About 100 mL of each of the three effluent samples were measured into three labelled beakers containing 0.5 g of the adsorbent. The samples were placed on a shaker set at 30°C and agitated uniformly for 30 minutes, after which the samples were centrifuged and filtered into sample bottles for determination of metal ion concentration using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS).

Adsorption of Heavy Metals from Effluents Using Almond Seed Shells (AMS)

The initial metal ion concentrations in the effluent were determined before adsorption for comparison purposes. A batch adsorption experiment was conducted to investigate the removal efficiency of Fe, Zn, and Pb ions using almond seed shells as the adsorbent. The adsorption process was conducted by adding varying doses of almond seed shells powder (0.1 g, 0.2 g, 0.3 g, 0.4 g, and 0.5 g) into the flasks containing the effluent. The flasks were placed in a thermostatic shaker and agitated at a constant speed of 150 rpm. The contact time was fixed at 30 minutes for each experiment, with the temperature maintained at 30°C to ensure uniform conditions. After 30

minutes of shaking, the mixture was filtered using Whatman filter paper to separate the almond seed shells powder from the effluent. The filtrate was collected for further analysis. The concentrations of Fe, Zn, and Pb ions in the treated effluent were determined using atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS). The removal efficiency (%) for each metal was calculated using the Equation 1

$$\text{Removal Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{C_i - C_f}{C_i} \times 100$$

Equation 1

Where: C_i is the initial concentration of the metal ions before adsorption. C_f is the final concentration of the metal ions after adsorption.

Preparation of Stock and Experimental Solutions

In this research, 1000 mg/L stock solutions of copper, lead, manganese, zinc and iron were prepared as follows using American Society for Testing Materials (ASTM) procedure:

Copper: Approximately 1.0 g of copper metal was dissolved in 50mL of 5.0 M nitric acid and diluted to 1 liter in a volumetric flask with deionized water.

Lead: Approximately 1.598 g of lead nitrate $Pb(NO_3)_2$ was dissolved in 100ml of deionized water and diluted to 1 liter in a volumetric flask with deionized water.

Manganese: Approximately 3.6077 g of manganese chloride ($MnCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$) was dissolved in 50ml concentrated hydrochloric acid and diluted to 1 litre in a volumetric flask with deionized water.

Zinc: Approximately 1.245 g of zinc oxide (ZnO) was dissolved in 5ml of deionized water followed by 25mL of 5M hydrochloric acid and then diluted to 1 litre in a volumetric flask with deionized water.

Iron: Approximately 0.6994 g of iron III oxide (Fe_2O_3) was dissolved in 20 mL of 5 M HCl and 5 ml of HNO_3 (sp. gr. 1.42) and diluted to 1 litre in a volumetric flask with deionized water. The stock solutions were stored in polythene bottles.

The experimental solutions (0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0 and 5.0 mg/L) of the metals were prepared by diluting aliquots of their respective stock solutions to the desired concentration. The concentration of each metal ion in the aqueous solution was confirmed by analysis using atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Evaluation of Equilibrium Properties

To evaluate the equilibrium properties, various solutions with initial metal ion concentration, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0 and 5.0 mg/L were prepared into 250 mL labelled beakers containing 0.5 g of the adsorbent. The samples were placed on Hei Dolph Unimax 2010 electric shaker and shaken continuously for 30 to 180 minutes at temperatures 30, 40, 50 and 60°C. The samples were then centrifuged at 450 rpm and the supernatant was filtered using Whatman No. 14 filter papers. The filtrates were immediately examined for

metal ion concentration using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The difference between the initial and the equilibrium concentrations gives the amount of ion adsorbed onto the adsorbent surface.

Variation of Initial Metal ion Concentration

Batch adsorption was carried out using initial metal ion concentrations of 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0 and 5.0 mg/L each for aqueous solutions of Fe, Cu, Pb, Mn and Zn. About 0.5 g of adsorbent was measured into each of five 250 ml beakers and 25 ml of 0.5 mg/L of each metal solution was added. The mixtures were placed on a shaker and agitated continuously at 30°C for 30 minutes after which the samples were centrifuged and filtered into clean sample bottles. The Hei Dolph Unimax 2010 electric shaker used has temperature adjustment. The filtrates were immediately examined for metal ion concentration using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The difference between the initial and the equilibrium concentrations determined the amount of ion adsorbed onto the adsorbent surface.

Variation of Contact Time

The effect of contact time on the adsorption of metal ion onto the adsorbent surface was studied at time 30, 60, 90, 120, 150 and 180 minutes. The study was carried out using 25 mL of each metal ion solution with initial concentration of 0.5 mg/L measured into five labelled beakers containing 0.5 g of the adsorbent. The beakers with content were placed on a shaker set at 30°C and agitated uniformly for 30 minutes. The experiment was repeated for other time intervals. The samples were then centrifuged and filtered into sample bottles for determination of metal ion concentration using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The amount of metal ions adsorbed was calculated using the Equation 2 (q_e) is given by:

$$\text{Equation 2} \quad q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_e) \cdot V}{m}$$

Where: q_e = Amount of metal ion adsorbed per gram of adsorbent (mg/g); C_0 = initial concentration of metal ion solution (mg/L); C_e = is the equilibrium concentration of the metal ion in the solution (mg/L); V = is volume of the solution(L); m = mass of the adsorbent (g).

Variation of Temperature

The adsorption of metal ions on the adsorbent surface was studied at temperatures 30, 40, 50 and 60°C. About 25 mL of each metal ion solution with initial concentration of 0.5 mg/L were measured into five labelled beakers containing 0.5 g of the adsorbent. The beakers with content were placed on a shaker with temperature set at 30°C and agitated uniformly for 30 minutes. The experiment was repeated for

other temperatures. The samples were then centrifuged and filtered into sample bottles for determination of metal ion concentration using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The amount of metal ions adsorbed was calculated using Equation 3 (q_e) given by:

$$q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_e) \cdot V}{m} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

Where: q_e = Amount of metal ion adsorbed per gram of adsorbent (mg/g); C_0 = initial concentration of metal ion solution (mg/L); C_e = is the equilibrium concentration of the metal ion in the solution (mg/L); V : is volume of the solution(L); m = mass of the adsorbent (g); The apparent activation energies (E_a) connected to the adsorption process were calculated using the Arrhenius equation. (Equation 4)

$$Y_t = A \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right) \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Where A is the Arrhenius constant, E_a is the activation energy, R is the universal gas constant, and Y_t is the quantity adsorbed at temperature T . A straight line was produced when $\log Y_t$ was plotted against $1/T$. The Arrhenius constant A and the apparent activation energy E_a might be found from the linear plots' slopes and intercepts, respectively

Variation of pH

The pH of the adsorption mixture was adjusted downwards by adding drops of 0.1 M HCl gradually, and upwards by drops of 0.1 M NaOH using dropping pipette. Buffers 4 and 10 were used to calibrate the pH meter. The effect of pH on the adsorption of metal ion onto the adsorbent surface was studied at pH 2, 6, 8 and 10. The experiment was carried out using 25 mL of each metal ion solution with initial concentration of 0.5 mg/L measured into five labelled beakers containing 0.5 g of the adsorbent. The mixtures were adjusted to pH 2, placed on a shaker set at 30°C and agitated uniformly for 30 minutes. The experiment was repeated for other pH values. The samples were centrifuged and filtered into sample bottles for determination of metal ion concentration using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The amount of metal ions adsorbed was determined by difference.

Adsorption Model Isotherms

The maximum adsorption capacity, adsorption mechanisms, equilibrium modeling, adsorbent-adsorbate interactions, and the dynamics of the adsorption process are all described by adsorption isotherms, which are empirical models. The Freundlich adsorption model, the pseudo-second order diffusion model, and the intraparticle diffusion model were fitted with the experimental findings to account for the adsorption of Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} from solutions containing almond seed

shell. The Freundlich adsorption isotherm model is given by Equation 5

$$\log x/m = \log k + n \log c \tag{Equation 5}$$

Where *c* is the concentration of the metal ion in solution, *k* and *n* are empirical constants, and *x/m* is the concentration of metal ion adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbent.

Adsorption Kinetics

For the adsorption of metal ions from solutions, many kinetic models, including pseudo-second order and intraparticle diffusion models, have been used to calculate the adsorption parameters. These metrics indicate which kinetic model fits the adsorption process's equilibrium data the best. The underlying premise of the pseudo-second order diffusion model is that the chemical adsorption involving valence forces through the sharing or exchange of electrons between the adsorbent and the adsorbate is the rate-limiting step in the adsorption process. Additionally, second-order kinetics is assumed to govern the adsorption process, with the rate of adsorption being proportional to the square of the difference between the amount of metal ions adsorbed at any given time and the equilibrium adsorption capacity. It is expressed as Equation 6

$$t/q_t = kq_e^2 + t/q_e \tag{Equation 6}$$

Where *q_e* and *q_t* are the amounts of adsorbate (mg/L) adsorbed at equilibrium and at contact time *t* (min), respectively and *k* is the pseudo-second order rate constant (min⁻¹).

Weber -Morris Intraparticle Diffusion Model

For the adsorption of Fe²⁺, Cu²⁺, Pb²⁺, Mn²⁺ and Zn²⁺ by almond seed shell, the intraparticle diffusion can be estimated using the Weber-Morris intraparticle diffusion model. According to this concept, the diffusion of the metal ions within the adsorbent's porous structure is the rate-limiting step in the adsorption process. It can be represented by Equation 7

$$q_t = k_{id}t^{1/2} + C \tag{Equation 7}$$

Where *t* is the contact time, *k_{id}* is the intraparticle diffusion rate constant (g Mg-1 min-1/2), *q_t* is the amount of metal ions adsorbed at time *t* (mg/g), and *C* is the intercept, which tells us about the thickness of the boundary layer (mg/g): the larger the intercept, the more surface sorption contributed to the rate-determining step (Weber and Morris 1963).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Metal ion concentration from Effluent Samples

As shown in **Table 2** the highest concentration of iron was found in the Niger Mill sample (15.3272 mg/L), which suggests a significant presence of iron contamination in this area. Sample from UNICROSS recorded the highest level of lead (5.1133 mg/L) in the adsorbent (AMS), which called for concern as lead is highly toxic, especially in urban environments. Manganese levels were generally elevated samples across all sites, with the highest concentration in sample from UNICROSS (2.8324 mg/L). Zinc was detected only in the Niger Mill sample (6.0094 mg/L), indicating a potential localized source of zinc contamination. Cadmium (Cd) and arsenic (As) were either not detected or present in very low concentrations (<0.0001 mg/L), suggesting limited contamination from these elements in the studied areas.

Nickel concentrations were below the detection limit in most samples, except in samples from UNICROSS where it was not detected, which suggests minimal contamination from Nickel. The results indicate that different industrial and urban activities in the Calabar Metropolis have contributed to varying levels of heavy metal contamination in the environment. The elevated levels of iron, lead, and manganese in certain locations absolutely called for concern due to their potential impact on public health and the environment. Additionally, the results indicated almond seed shells from UNICAL to be free from heavy metals contaminations, thereby adjudging to be effective for heavy metals removals from aqueous medium.

Table 2: Concentration of metal ions from effluent samples and adsorbents

Sample(mg/L)	Fe	Zn	Pb	Cd	Cr	As	Mn	Ni
Niger Mill	15.3272	6.0094	3.2892	<0.0001	0.0602	ND	1.6940	<0.0001
Top Feed	2.1521	<0.0001	1.3014	<0.0001	ND	ND	1.7361	<0.0001
Wapi Junction	1.4570	ND	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0172	ND	1.2191	<0.0001
UNICAL (AMS)	8.4182	ND	1.9270	<0.0001	ND	ND	2.7984	<0.0001
UNICROSS (AMS)	3.4434	ND	5.1133	<0.0001	ND	ND	2.8324	ND

Table 2a and **Figure 1** shows that the quantity of metal ions adsorbed from the effluent sample increases with an increase in the adsorbent dose. As the adsorbent dose increases, the available surface area and the number of adsorption sites for the metal ions also increases.

Thus, the quantity of metals ions adsorbed onto these active sites on the adsorbent surface increases with increase in adsorbent dose. **Figure 1** also shows that the quantity of metal ions adsorbed follows the sequence Fe²⁺>Zn²⁺>Pb²⁺. This implies that the quantity of the metal ions adsorbed by adsorbent

from the effluent sample would depend on the initial metal ion concentration. This is because the higher initial metal ion concentration provides more metal ions available for adsorption onto the adsorbent surface. **Table 2b** shows that the initial metal ion concentration of the effluent sample is in the order

$Fe^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Pb^{2+}$. Almond seed shells show great adsorption capacity for the metal ions investigated and can be effectively applied in the treatment of industrial effluents and water suspected to be contaminated with heavy metals.

Figure 1: Variation of quantity of metal ion adsorbed with adsorbent dose

Table 2a. Concentration of highly contaminated metal ions adsorbed from Niger Mill effluent by AMS in 30 minutes at 30°C

Adsorbent dose (g)	Fe (mg/L)	Zn (mg/L)	Pb (mg/L)
0.1	0.4721	0.4357	0.2259
0.2	1.2583	1.0418	0.6663
0.3	2.8065	1.7320	1.1804
0.4	3.7746	2.4639	1.8511
0.5	4.8622	3.6705	2.6136

Table 2b. Initial highly Contaminated metal ion concentrations of Niger Mill effluent

Sample ID	Fe (mg/L)	Zn (mg/L)	Pb (mg/L)
Niger Mill Effluent	15.3272	6.0094	3.2892

Effect of Concentration on the Removal of Metals Ions from Solution of Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Zn^{2+}

As presented in **Tables 3a-b**, the results indicate that the rate of adsorption increased as the concentration of metal ions increased. The reason for this is that when the concentration of metal ions increases, there are more ions available to be absorbed into the adsorbent surface [22]. The ability of the adsorbent to draw in and hold on to adsorbate molecules is demonstrated by the plot of quantity adsorbed versus metal ion concentration in **Figure 2** which exhibits a constant and increasing rate of adsorption for all the metals under study. **Figure 2:** Variation of quantity of metal ion adsorbed by AMS with concentration at 30°C

Table 3a. AAS reading for variation of initial metal ion concentration (C_o) for 30 minutes at 30°C

	0.5 mg/L	1.0 mg/L	2.0 mg/L	3.0 mg/L	4.0 mg/L	5.0 mg/L
Fe	0.1691	0.3935	0.9311	1.0435	1.2525	1.6508
Cu	0.0895	0.0968	0.1831	0.2568	0.3044	0.5096
Pb	0.1129	0.3675	0.4992	0.5674	0.6885	0.9408
Mn	0.0425	0.0011	0.0008	0.0104	0.0013	0.0184
Zn	0.2608	0.4870	0.2533	1.4643	1.7077	2.0817

Table 3b. Concentration of the metal ions adsorbed at 30°C

Initial concentration (C_o) mg/L	$C_o - C_t$ (mg/L)				
	Fe^{2+}	Cu^{2+}	Pb^{2+}	Mn^{2+}	Zn^{2+}
0.5	0.3309	0.4105	0.3871	0.4575	0.2392
1.0	0.6065	0.9032	0.6325	0.9989	0.5130
2.0	1.0689	1.8169	1.5008	1.9992	0.7467
3.0	1.9565	2.7432	2.4326	2.9896	1.5357
4.0	2.7475	3.6956	3.3115	3.9987	2.2923
5.0	3.3492	4.4904	4.0592	4.9816	2.9183

Effect of Contact Time on the Removal of Metals Ions Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} From Solutions

The findings in **Figure 3** and **Table 4a-b** demonstrate how the concentration of metal ions adsorbed increase over time. These results showed the increasing percentage of metal ions migrating from the bulk solution onto the adsorbent's active sites over time via the adsorbent boundary layer [24]. The continual disruption of the boundary layer between the bulk solution and the adsorbent surface, which permits more adsorption to occur, is responsible for the rise in sorption of the metal ions with increasing agitation time. According to Okuo and Ozioko [24], it is likewise linked to a rise in the kinetic energy of the hydrated metal ions. The different sorption processes ion-exchange, adsorption (physisorption/chemisorption), coordination, and complexation caused by the different kinds of ion

binding groups such as hydroxyl, carboxylic, and phenolic functional groups in the adsorbent—could also be responsible for the removal of metal ions by almond seed shell [21].

The availability of the adsorbent's exposed surface area may have contributed to the initial faster rate seen in Figure 3, since the adsorption kinetics rely on the adsorbent's surface area [21]. Over time, the five metal ions' adsorption onto the adsorbent surface increased steadily. The adsorption process decreased with increasing time and the amount of adsorbate covering the adsorbent surface. $Mn^{2+} > Cu^{2+} > Pb^{2+} > Fe^{2+} > Zn^{2+}$ is the pattern in the amount of metal ions adsorbed.

Figure 3: Variation of quantity of ion adsorbed by AMS with time at 30°C

Table 4a : AAS reading for variation of Contact time with 0.5 mg/L metal ion concentration at 30 °C.

	30 min	60 min	90 min	120 min	150 min	180 min
Fe	0.2924	0.2018	0.1785	0.1463	0.1372	0.1319
Cu	0.1948	0.1026	0.0691	0.0584	0.0480	0.0443
Pb	0.2360	0.1725	0.1332	0.1171	0.1150	0.1042
Mn	0.1854	0.0778	0.0441	0.0369	0.0124	0.0101
Zn	0.3137	0.2410	0.2029	0.1818	0.1785	0.1713

Table 4b: Concentration of the metal ions adsorbed at various time interval at 30°C

Time (min.)	$C_0 - C_t$ (mg/L)				
	Fe	Cu	Pb	Mn	Zn
30	0.2076	0.3052	0.2640	0.3146	0.1863
60	0.2982	0.3974	0.3275	0.4222	0.2590
90	0.3215	0.4309	0.3668	0.4559	0.2971
120	0.3537	0.4416	0.3829	0.4631	0.3182
150	0.3628	0.4520	0.3850	0.4876	0.3215
180	0.3681	0.4557	0.3958	0.4899	0.3287

Effect of Temperature on the Removal of Fe²⁺, Cu²⁺, Pb²⁺, Mn²⁺, and Zn²⁺ From Aqueous Solutions

An increase in temperature led to a more effective adsorption of the metal ions by the adsorbent, as shown in **Tables 5a-b** and **Figure 4**. The higher kinetic energy of the metal ions is most likely to be the cause of this. The collision frequency between the metal ions and the adsorbent surface will be more enhanced at higher kinetic energy levels, which will improve the adsorbent's removal efficiency for the metal ions [12]. The reason behind this could also be

that at elevated temperatures, the bonds between the adsorbate molecules and the solvent (such water) become less strong, facilitating the adsorbate molecules' separation from the solvent and subsequent adsorption onto the adsorbent surface. Thus, a rise in temperature increases affinity for the highly mobilized metal ions and broadens the surface area available for adsorption at the adsorbent surface. Certain scholars have proposed that there are two types of adsorption mechanisms physical adsorption and chemisorption for sorption from aqueous solutions. From **Figure 5**, the size of the apparent activation energy for the process of adsorption sheds

light on the characteristics of the adsorption mechanism. Table 6 displays the estimated values of the Arrhenius constant and activation energy derived from the plots' intercepts and slopes, respectively. Activation energy (E_a) and Arrhenius constant (A) are calculated values shown in Table 6. Cu, Pb, and Mn adsorption on almond seed shells had E_a values less than 40 kJ/mol, whereas Fe and Zn adsorption values are 44.56 kJ/mol and 64.27 kJ/mol, respectively. This suggests that the almond seed

shell's adsorption rate for Fe and Zn is comparatively slow and that it will take more time to reach its maximal adsorption capacity. It also shows that, as seen in Figure 5, temperature has a significant impact on the rate of adsorption. As a result of providing the energy required to cross the activation barrier, a temperature increase greatly increases the adsorption rate [21].

Figure 4: Variation of metal ion adsorbed by AMS with temperature

Table 5a. AAS reading for variation of temperature with 0.5 mg/L metal ion

mg/L	30°C	40°C	50°C	60°C
Fe	0.1691	0.1379	0.0952	0.0189
Cu	0.0895	0.0701	0.0597	0.0319
Pb	0.1129	0.1065	0.0822	0.0515
Mn	0.0625	0.0382	0.0174	0.0056
Zn	0.2608	0.2293	0.1685	0.0954

Table 5b: Concentration of the metal ions adsorbed at various temperatures

Temp (°C)	$C_o - C_t$ (mg/L)				
	Fe	Cu	Pb	Mn	Zn
30	0.3309	0.4105	0.3871	0.4375	0.2392
40	0.3621	0.4299	0.3935	0.4618	0.2707
50	0.4048	0.4403	0.4178	0.4826	0.3315
60	0.4811	0.4681	0.4485	0.4944	0.4046

Table 6. Calculated values of activation energy E_a and Arrhenius constant A .

	Fe	Cu	Pb	Mn	Zn
Activation energy (kJ/mol)	44.56	15.05	18.12	14.80	64.27
Arrhenius constant	0.5320	0.4847	0.4660	0.5193	0.4762

Effect of pH on the Removal of Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} from Solutions

The adsorption of metal ions is greatly impacted by pH because it affects the adsorbent's surface charge, the metal ions' solubility and speciation, and the process' overall efficiency [25]. In conditions of severe acidity, the metal ions are discharged fully [26]. The adsorbent surface may be positively charged at low pH levels, which can reject cationic metal ions and lessen their adsorption. The adsorbent surface may become more negatively charged when pH rises, which would enable the adsorption of

cationic metal ions through electrostatic interactions. The speciation of metal ions in the solution can also be impacted by the pH of the solution. The metal ions might exist as hydroxide complexes, other complex species, or free metal ions at different pH levels. Thus, the chemical form that the metal ions take in the solution would determine how they adsorb [27]. Table 7 demonstrates how increasing the pH from an acidic (pH 2) to an alkaline (pH 10) state increased the concentration of metal ions adsorbed. This suggests that the alkaline medium supports the adsorption process more than the acidic media. This is shown in Figure 7. In every instance, the experimental data fit into the Freundlich isotherm with a data reliability (R^2) of greater than 97%. The intercepts and slopes of the plots were used to compute the values of k and n . Favorable adsorption is defined by the Freundlich adsorption model as occurring when n is larger than 1. According to Table 8, a positive adsorption of the metal ions on the adsorbent is indicated by values of n larger than 1 for the adsorption of Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} onto almond seed shell. The experimental data for the adsorption of Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} by AMS suit the pseudo-second order adsorption kinetic model (Ho and Mckay 1999) according to the plots of t/q against t (min) for these adsorptions (Figure. 8) appendix page. Table 9 displays the values of k and q that were determined using the plots' slopes and intercepts together with the accompanying correlation coefficient values. These results indicate that the pseudo-second-order kinetic model [21] may provide the most accurate description of the AMS's adsorption of Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} . Table 9 shows the values of $k_{id} \times$ and C derived from the slopes and intercepts of the plots of qt versus $t^{1/2}$.

The fact that Figure 8's plots' starting points are linear but do not cross the origin raises the possibility that the rate-limiting step is the diffusion of metal ions inside the adsorbent's porous structure. Nevertheless, the plot of qt vs $t^{1/2}$ diverges from linearity and the spots become dispersed as the adsorption process achieves equilibrium. This

discrepancy suggests that additional factors, such as the availability of adsorption sites, may affect the overall kinetics of the adsorption process, which is no longer exclusively governed by intraparticle diffusion.

Figure 6: Variation of quantity of ion adsorbed by AMS with pH

Table 7a. AAS reading for variation of pH with 0.5 mg/L metal ion concentration at 30 minutes and 30°C

	pH 2	pH 6	pH 8	pH 10
Fe	0.2638	0.1356	0.1147	0.0932
Cu	0.1970	0.0824	0.0612	0.0557
Pb	0.2176	0.1065	0.0822	0.0515
Mn	0.1638	0.0320	0.0221	0.0175
Zn	0.2913	0.1748	0.1486	0.1130

Table 8. Freundlich adsorption isotherm empirical constants

Metal ions	Almond seed shell		
	<i>N</i>	<i>K</i>	<i>R</i> ²
Fe ²⁺	1.02	1.25	0.9900
Cu ²⁺	1.04	1.74	0.9991
Pb ²⁺	1.06	1.46	0.9923
Mn ²⁺	1.03	1.93	0.9993
Zn ²⁺	1.07	0.95	0.9762

Table 7b. Concentration of metal ions adsorbed at different pH

pH	<i>C</i> ₀ - <i>C</i> _i (mg/L)				
	Fe	Cu	Pb	Mn	Zn
2	0.2362	0.3030	0.2824	0.3362	0.2087
6	0.3644	0.4176	0.3905	0.4680	0.3252
8	0.3853	0.4388	0.4187	0.4779	0.3514
10	0.4068	0.4443	0.4253	0.4825	0.3870

Table 9. Kinetic parameters for the adsorption of metal ions from solution on almond seed shell (AMS)

Pseudo-second order models	Parameters	Fe	Cu	Pb	Mn	Zn
	<i>q</i> _e (mg g ⁻¹)		0.0060	0.0070	0.0061	0.0076
<i>K</i> ₂ (g mg ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)		333.65	501.85	508.55	397.24	372.89
<i>R</i> ²		0.9981	0.9991	0.9994	0.9987	0.9979
Intraparticle diffusion models	<i>k</i> _{id} × 10 ⁻⁴ (g mg ⁻¹ min ^{-1/2})	10.0	9.0	8.0	1.0	9.0
	<i>C</i> (mg g ⁻¹)	0.0063	0.0119	0.0097	0.0117	0.0056
	<i>R</i> ²	0.9049	0.8494	0.905	0.8637	0.8996

Figure 7: Freundlich adsorption isotherm for the adsorption of metal ions from

CONCLUSION

This study explored almond seed shells as an effective and affordable adsorbent for removing Fe²⁺, Cu²⁺, Pb²⁺, Mn²⁺, and Zn²⁺ from waste water. Almond seed shells demonstrated strong adsorption capabilities influenced by factors like temperature, pH, contact time, initial metal ion concentration, and adsorbent dosage. The Freundlich adsorption model was employed, it revealed favorable adsorption indicated by 'n' values consistently exceeding 1 for all metal ions tested. Adsorption followed the order Mn²⁺ > Cu²⁺ > Pb²⁺ > Fe²⁺ > Zn²⁺, suggesting varying affinities of almond seed shells for different metals. Kinetic studies supported the pseudo-second-order model, indicating that chemical adsorption is the rate-limiting step in the process. Importantly, the use of almond seed shells is highlighted for its renewability, affordability, and environmental friendliness, making it a promising option for wastewater treatment.

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